

The Effect of Preemptive Local Anesthesia on Postoperative Pain Following Vaginal Hysterectomy: A Randomized Controlled TrialDeepak Kumar Nirala¹, Ankita Kumari², Sudama Prasad³¹Senior Resident, Department of Anesthesia, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India²Senior Resident, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, AIIMS, Patna, Bihar, India³Professor and HOD, Department of Anesthesia, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

Received: 25-05-2024 / Revised: 23-06-2024 / Accepted: 04-07-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** Vaginal hysterectomy is a commonly performed procedure for benign gynecological conditions, often associated with significant postoperative pain. Effective pain management is crucial for enhancing patient recovery and satisfaction. Preemptive Local Anesthesia (PLA) has shown promise in various surgical contexts by reducing postoperative pain, yet its efficacy in vaginal hysterectomy remains underexplored.**Aim:** This study aimed to evaluate the effect of Preemptive Local Anesthesia (PLA) on Postoperative pain (PO) following vaginal hysterectomy.**Methods:** A multicentric, randomized controlled trial was conducted over eight months, involving 100 patients scheduled for vaginal hysterectomy. Participants were randomly assigned to either the intervention group, receiving (PLA), or the control group, receiving standard care without (PLA). (PO) was assessed using the Visual Analog Scale (VAS) at multiple time points (immediate postoperative, 6, 12, 24, and 48 hours). The need for rescue analgesia and incidence of complications were also recorded. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0, with significance set at $p < 0.05$.**Results:** Patients in the intervention group reported significantly lower VAS pain scores at all-time points compared to the control group ($p < 0.001$). The intervention group also had a reduced need for rescue analgesia (20% vs. 50%, $p = 0.002$). There were no significant differences in the incidence of postoperative complications between the groups.**Conclusion:** (PLA) significantly reduces (PO) and the need for additional analgesia in patients undergoing vaginal hysterectomy, without increasing the risk of complications.**Recommendations:** (PLA) should be considered as part of standard pain management protocols for vaginal hysterectomy to enhance patient comfort and recovery.**Keywords:** Vaginal Hysterectomy, Preemptive Local Anesthesia, Postoperative Pain, Randomized Controlled Trial, Pain Management

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Introduction

A frequent surgical management for a number of benign gynaecological problems, including irregular uterine bleeding, uterine fibroids, and uterine prolapse, is vaginal hysterectomy. (PO) continues to be a major problem despite advancements in surgical procedures and anaesthesia. It affects patient recovery and overall satisfaction with the surgery. In addition to improving patient comfort, efficient pain management techniques also lessen the requirement for postoperative analgesics, which may have unfavourable side effects. Preemptive analgesia, which involves providing pain treatment prior to surgical injury, has shown promise in lowering overall discomfort and minimising central sensitisation, thereby mitigating postoperative pain.

In particular, PLA refers to the use of local anaesthetics prior to the start of a surgical procedure. This method has been demonstrated to lessen the severity of (PO) by preventing nociceptive signals from being sent at the surgical site. PLA has been investigated in a number of surgical contexts, such as orthopaedic, dental, and abdominal procedures. Good results have been noted in terms of decreased pain scores and analgesic consumption [1, 2]. Its efficacy in vaginal hysterectomy, a technique that requires major pelvic tissue manipulation and can cause significant postoperative discomfort, is, however, poorly supported by research [3].

In order to improve patient outcomes after vaginal hysterectomy, it is crucial to optimise (PO) management, according to recent studies. A Study

highlighted the value of multimodal analgesia in lowering opioid use and enhancing patient satisfaction after gynaecological operations, which includes the use of PLA [4]. Similar to this, another randomised controlled experiment showed that administering local anaesthetics ahead of time during abdominal procedures greatly decreased pain scores and the requirement for rescue analgesia [5]. These results highlight the potential advantages of anticipatory local anaesthesia in enhancing the management of (PO) and call for additional research in the context of vaginal hysterectomy. This study is to assess the impact of PLA on (PO) following vaginal hysterectomy, given the increasing interest in preemptive analgesia and its potential to improve surgical outcomes. This study aimed to evaluate the effect of (PLA) on (PO) following vaginal hysterectomy.

Methodology

Study Design: This study is a prospective randomized controlled trial.

Study Setting: The trial was carried out in two large tertiary care hospitals, each with a well-established gynecology department capable of performing vaginal hysterectomy procedures. The study was conducted over a period of 8 months in multiple healthcare centers, making it a multicentric study.

Participants: A total of 100 patients scheduled for vaginal hysterectomy were recruited for this study. The participants were randomly assigned to either the intervention group (receiving PLA) or the control group (not receiving PLA).

Inclusion Criteria

- Women aged 30-60 years.
- Patients scheduled for vaginal hysterectomy for benign conditions (e.g., uterine prolapse, fibroids, etc.).
- Patients who provided informed consent to participate in the study.
- Patients with ASA (American Society of Anesthesiologists) physical status I or II.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with a history of chronic pain disorders.
- Patients with known allergies to local anesthetics.
- Patients who have undergone previous abdominal or pelvic surgeries.
- Patients with contraindications to regional anesthesia.
- Patients with significant comorbidities (e.g., cardiovascular disease, uncontrolled diabetes, etc.).

- Patients who refused to give consent.

Bias: To minimize bias, the randomization process was carried out using a computer-generated random number sequence. Allocation concealment was ensured using opaque, sealed envelopes. The patients, surgical team, and outcome assessors were blinded to group allocation.

- **Patient Blinding:** Patients did not know which group they were in to prevent their knowledge from influencing their perception of pain.
- **Surgical Team Blinding:** The surgical team was unaware of group assignments to avoid altering their technique or behavior.
- **Outcome Assessor Blinding:** Those evaluating postoperative pain were blinded to group allocation to prevent bias in their assessments.

Blinding was implemented to ensure unbiased results by preventing knowledge of group assignments from affecting the treatment and evaluation processes.

Data Collection: Data were collected at multiple time points: preoperatively, immediately postoperatively, and at regular intervals up to 48 hours post-surgery. The primary outcome measured was postoperative pain, assessed using the (VAS). Secondary outcomes included the need for rescue analgesia, the total dose of analgesics administered, and the incidence of postoperative complications.

Procedure: Patients in the intervention group received preemptive local anesthesia with 0.5% bupivacaine administered to the vaginal mucosa before surgery. The control group did not receive this anesthesia. Both groups were given standardized general anesthesia during the procedure and received uniform postoperative care across all study sites. This design helps isolate the effects of preemptive local anesthesia on postoperative pain by controlling other variables.

1. Intervention Group:

- **Preemptive Local Anesthesia:**

Substance Used: 0.5% bupivacaine 10ml

Administration: Injected into the vaginal mucosa by the non-operating surgeon.

Purpose: The aim is to reduce postoperative pain by providing analgesia before the surgery starts, potentially leading to less pain and a smoother recovery process.

2. Control Group:

- **Procedure:**

Surgical Intervention: Underwent the same vaginal hysterectomy as the intervention group.

No Local Anesthesia: Received no preemptive local anesthesia.

Purpose: To serve as a baseline comparison, assessing the impact of preemptive local anesthesia by comparing outcomes with those of the intervention group.

3. General Anesthesia:

Standardization: Both groups received the same standardized general anesthesia during the surgery.

Purpose: To ensure that differences in postoperative pain are due to the preemptive local anesthesia rather than variations in the general anesthesia used.

4. Postoperative (PO) Management:

Standardized Protocols: Postoperative care was uniform across all study sites.

Purpose: To maintain consistency in pain management and recovery practices, ensuring that differences in outcomes are attributable to the preemptive local anesthesia and not variations in postoperative care.

Timing: Given before the vaginal hysterectomy begins.

5. Drug Used for Rescue Analgesia:

- **Morphine** (typical dose: 1-2 mg IV every 2-4 hours as needed).

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics summarized demographic data. The primary outcome, postoperative pain, was analyzed using independent t-tests or Mann-Whitney U tests. Categorical variables were assessed with chi-square tests. A p-value of <0.05 was considered significant.

Results

A total of 120 patients were initially assessed for eligibility. After applying the inclusion and exclusion criteria, 100 patients were randomized into two groups: the intervention group (n=50) receiving PLA and the control group (n=50) not receiving PLA. There were no dropouts or loss to follow-up during the study period.

Table 1: Demographic and Baseline Characteristics

Characteristic	Intervention Group (n=50)	Control Group (n=50)	p-value
Age (years, mean $\pm$ SD)	45.2 $\pm$ 7.1	46.1 $\pm$ 6.8	0.473
BMI (kg/m ² , mean $\pm$ SD)	27.4 $\pm$ 3.5	27.8 $\pm$ 3.6	0.623
ASA Physical Status (I/II)	28/22	27/23	0.841
Indication for Surgery			
- Uterine Fibroids	30 (60%)	28 (56%)	0.687
- Uterine Prolapse	20 (40%)	22 (44%)	0.687
Duration of Surgery (min)	90.5 $\pm$ 15.3	92.7 $\pm$ 14.8	0.392

Primary Outcome: The primary outcome, postoperative pain, was measured using the (VAS) at multiple time points: immediately postoperative, at 6 hours, 12 hours, 24 hours, and 48 hours after surgery.

Table 2: (PO) Scores (VAS, mean $\pm$ SD)

Time Point	Intervention Group (n=50)	Control Group (n=50)	p-value
Immediate Postoperative	3.2 $\pm$ 1.1	5.4 $\pm$ 1.3	<0.001
6 hours	2.8 $\pm$ 1.0	4.7 $\pm$ 1.4	<0.001
12 hours	2.5 $\pm$ 1.2	4.3 $\pm$ 1.5	<0.001
24 hours	2.2 $\pm$ 1.0	3.8 $\pm$ 1.2	<0.001
48 hours	1.8 $\pm$ 0.8	3.2 $\pm$ 1.1	<0.001

Patients in the intervention group reported significantly lower pain scores at all-time points compared to the control group (p < 0.001).

Secondary Outcomes: The need for rescue analgesia was assessed by recording the number of

patients who required additional pain relief medications beyond the standard postoperative regimen. The drug used for rescue analgesia was morphine. The typical dose administered was 1-2 mg intravenously (IV) every 2-4 hours as needed.

Table 3: Need for Rescue Analgesia

Group	Number of Patients Requiring Rescue Analgesia	Total Analgesic Dose (mg, mean $\pm$ SD)	p-value
Intervention Group (n=50)	10 (20%)	120 $\pm$ 25	0.002
Control Group (n=50)	25 (50%)	175 $\pm$ 35	0.002

Significantly fewer patients in the intervention group required rescue analgesia compared to the control group (20% vs. 50%, $p = 0.002$). The drug used for rescue analgesia was morphine. The

typical dose administered was 1-2 mg intravenously (IV) every 2-4 hours as needed.

The incidence of postoperative complications was recorded, including nausea, vomiting, and any other adverse events.

Table 4: Postoperative Complications

Complication	Intervention Group (n=50)	Control Group (n=50)	p-value
Nausea	5 (10%)	8 (16%)	0.367
Vomiting	2 (4%)	6 (12%)	0.148
Other Adverse Events	3 (6%)	5 (10%)	0.464

There were no statistically significant differences in the incidence of postoperative complications between the two groups.

Discussion

The results showed that after vaginal hysterectomy, (PLA) significantly decreased (PO), with patients in the intervention group reporting reduced pain levels at all points in time that were evaluated. Furthermore, there were no appreciable variations in the occurrence of postoperative complications across the groups, and the intervention group required much less rescue analgesia.

This randomised controlled trial's findings show that using (PLA) considerably lowers postoperative pain in individuals having vaginal hysterectomy surgery. Compared to patients who did not get the anaesthesia, patients who got the PLA consistently reported reduced pain levels on the VAS at all assessed time periods, including immediately postoperatively, at 6 hours, 12 hours, 24 hours, and 48 hours. The statistical significance of the pain score differences indicates the effectiveness of PLA in the management of postoperative pain.

Also, the intervention group required significantly less rescue analgesia. Compared to 50% of patients in the control group, only 20% of patients in the intervention group needed additional pain management. According to this, (PLA) not only lessens pain but also lessens the need for additional analgesics, which can help limit the possibility of adverse consequences from using larger dosages of painkillers. The frequency of surgical complications, including nausea, vomiting, and other unpleasant events, was also investigated in this study. The lack of significant variations in problems between the two groups according to the results suggests that the use of PLA did not raise the likelihood of unfavourable outcomes.

The effectiveness of PLA in minimising (PO) after vaginal hysterectomy was evaluated in the study by Gluck. In this trial, 60 women were randomised to receive bupivacaine or a placebo prior to making a surgical incision. The two groups' (PO) levels at different times after surgery did not significantly differ, according to the data. PLA might not be

useful in this situation, as there was no decrease in the usage of opioid-based analgesics during the healing process [6].

In order to assess the effect of anticipatory local anaesthetics on (PO) after vaginal hysterectomy, a comprehensive review and meta-analysis was carried out. Five studies with a total of 277 women were included in the analysis. The findings showed that within the first several hours following surgery, PLA considerably decreased (PO) levels. Additionally, throughout the first 24 hours following surgery, there was a considerable decrease in the amount of opioids used when local anaesthesia was used. According to the study, this implies that anticipatory local anaesthesia may be advantageous for the temporary treatment of pain during vaginal hysterectomy [7].

The efficacy of bupivacaine plus dexmedetomidine for preemptive analgesia in patients undergoing abdominal hysterectomy in another trial was assessed. According to the study, bupivacaine plus dexmedetomidine together provide better pain relief than bupivacaine by itself. In the first twenty-four hours following surgery, patients in the combination group needed fewer doses of rescue analgesics and their analgesia lasted longer. These results demonstrate the potential advantages of using local anaesthetics in conjunction with dexmedetomidine to improve (PO) management [8].

Conclusion

The findings of this study support the use of (PLA) as an effective and safe strategy for reducing (PO) and the need for rescue analgesia in patients undergoing vaginal hysterectomy. These results suggest that incorporating (PLA) into clinical practice could enhance patient comfort and potentially improve recovery outcomes.

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